

Solvent effects on the charge transfer complexes between *p*-chloranil and 2,2'-bipyridine and 1,10-phenanthroline^ψ

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Complex formation between *p*-chloranil (Cl-Q) and the heterocyclic aromatic donors like 2,2'-bipyridine (bipy) and 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) were studied in different aliphatic and aromatic solvents. The complexes are found to be considerably stable in different solvents. The comparable values of both Cl-Q + bipy and Cl-Q + phen suggest that the complexes are similar in nature. Acceptor being the same for both the complexes, the differences in Gibbs energy changes for the Cl-Q + bipy and Cl-Q + phen complexes reflect the differences of the Gibbs energy values of the complexes and donors. The differences in the Gibbs energy values for the two complexes arise from the greater resonance stabilization and coplanarity of phen compared to bipy. However, the change from *trans*-form of bipy to *cis*-form is likely to make Cl-Q + bipy complex coplanar. The effect of solvents on the stability of the complexes has been found to be marginal but similar.

The association constants of the complexes are greater in aliphatic solvents compared to those in aromatic solvents where the values are almost the same.

Attempts to correlate ΔG^0 values with different solvent parameters like $1/\epsilon$, $(\epsilon-1)/(2\epsilon-1)$ and E_T (30) values have been made. Two straight lines, one for aliphatic solvents and other for aromatic solvents has been obtained. But no singular parameter is capable of giving satisfactory explanation regarding the solvent effects of the complexes.

A preliminary report on the studies of solvent effects on the charge transfer complexes between chloranil (Cl-Q) and 2,2'-bipyridine (bipy) and 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) was made¹. Recently Mandal and Lahiri² made studies on the charge-transfer complexes between benzoquinone and aforesaid ligands.

The purpose of the present investigation is to throw more light on the Cl-Q + bipy and Cl-Q + phen complexes.

The results are reported in this communication.

Result

The association constant K for the reaction

can be written as

$$K_{DA} = \frac{[DA]}{[D][A]} \cdot \frac{\gamma_{DA}}{\gamma_D \gamma_A} \approx \frac{[DA]}{[D][A]} \quad (2)$$

In dilute solutions of neutral molecules, $\frac{\gamma_{DA}}{\gamma_D \gamma_A}$ has been assumed to be unity^{1,2}.

D and A are taken in equivalent proportions and an iterative procedure utilizing the equation.

$$\frac{C_1}{(d_2 - d_1)} = \frac{1}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)l} + \frac{1}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)(C_2 - x)l} \cdot \frac{1}{K_{DA}} \quad (3)$$

have been utilized to calculate K in the way described before¹⁻⁵. In this expression C_1 and C_2 are the initial concentrations of A and D, ϵ_1 , d_1 and ϵ_2 , d_2 are the extinction coefficients and absorptivity values of chloranil (A) and complex respectively and x = equilibrium concentration of AD

$$x = \frac{d_2 - d_1}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)l} \quad (4)$$

The results are presented in Table 1.

^ψDedicated to Professor Y. K. Gupta on his 80th birth anniversary.

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Table 1. Equilibrium constants, free energy changes and extinction coefficient values of donor-acceptor complexes in different solvents at 298 K

Sl. no.	Solvents	λ_{\max} (nm)	Acceptor : Chloranil					
			Donor : 2,2'-Bipyridine			Donor : 1, 10-Phenanthroline		
			Extinction coefficient of complex $\times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	Equilibrium constants $K_{\text{DA}} \times 10^{-2} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	ΔG^0 kJ mol^{-1}	Extinction coefficient of complex $\times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	Equilibrium constants $K_{\text{DA}} \times 10^{-2} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	ΔG^0 kJ mol^{-1}
1.	Benzene	336	21.75	1.00	-11.41	72.55	2.29	-13.46
2.	Toluene	360	19.72	1.00	-11.42	30.11	2.28	-13.45
3.	<i>o</i> -Xylene	388	47.99	1.03	-11.49	1.95	2.21	-13.38
4.	Mesitylene	416	17.79	1.02	-11.46	2.85	2.19	-13.35
5.	Dichloromethane	377	6.24	2.72	-13.89	60.13	7.86	-16.52
6.	Chloroform	374	1.69	1.76	-12.82	0.69	2.57	-13.75
7.	Carbontetrachloride	370	2.73	1.98	-13.11	4.50	2.64	-13.82

Discussion

The interpretation of the solvent effects on the association constants of the complexes is difficult as it is associated with several inherent limitations. These are :

(i) The change in the standard states with change in solvent systems which has to be ignored.

(ii) For the reaction (1), the values of $\frac{\gamma_{\text{DA}}}{\gamma_{\text{D}}\gamma_{\text{A}}}$ may change slightly with change in solvent systems.

(iii) There is lack of singular property which can be utilized for the proper correlation of data.

In spite of the limitations, attempts should be made to understand the role of the solvents on the H-bonding, CT interaction and other interactions and the stability of the complexes. Both bipy and phen exhibit two intense bands at (233 nm and 281 nm) and (228 nm and 264 nm) corresponding to β and β' -bands^{6,7}. However, bipy is present in *trans*-form in organic solvents where free rotation is possible but phen is rigid, coplanar and associated with resonance stabilisation⁸. Both the compounds have the capability to undergo $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. However, absorption bands are almost insensitive to solvents and the absorption spectra suggest $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ rather than $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions⁹.

Chloranil, show both $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ as well as $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions and the spectral solvent shift in the region 370–400 nm should be due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. However, the complexes formed between Cl-Q and bipy or phen show slight or no shift in the absorption maxima though considerable changes in absorptivity occur similar to those observed by other workers^{10,11}. The molecules have dipole moments. Thus dipole-dipole, dipole-induced dipole, dispersion in-

teractions together with CT and hydrogen bonding interactions of the components and complexes may be the reasons for slight or no shift in the absorption maxima of the complexes.

The K_{DA} values have been found to be fairly high. The complexes are almost equally stable and comparable in nature similar to those found in case of Q + bipy and Q + phen complexes. The possibility of complex formation likes AS or DS may vitiate the result as solute-solvent interaction is an universal phenomenon in all solvation processes. However, negligible or marginal spectral solvent shift of D (bipy or phen) eliminates the possibility of DS complexation⁹. Reports of CT-complex formation between chloranil with solvents like benzene, chloroform etc. in heptane^{12,13} (assuming no complex formation in heptane) are known. But the contribution due to possible formation of (AS) has been adequately compensated taking (A) in respective solvents as blank and the donors do not absorb.

The comparable values of the association constants K_{DA} between the Q or Cl-Q with the donors (bipy and phen) and a reasonable constancy of the values in all the solvents suggest that the nature of the complexes are similar and almost equally stable though Q-complexes have greater stability compared to those of Cl-Q complexes and phen complexes have greater stability than bipy complexes². The acceptor being the same, the difference in Gibbs energy changes reflects the differences in Gibbs energy values of the complexes and the donors. The near equality of the K_{DA} -values is, therefore, surprising, as phen is co-planar having C₁₁-C₁₂ bond fixed whereas there is possibility of free rotation in bipy (around C₁-C₁ bonds) making it non-coplanar and bipy is present in the *trans*-form in the organic solvents^{6,7,14-17}. Considerable resonance stabilization is possible in phen compared to bipy⁸. The λ_{\max} of phen is

around 264 nm whereas λ_{\max} of bipy is around 281 nm, indicating considerable energy differences in transition of phen and bipy. However, the difference in energy values may be partially compensated due to conversion of *trans*- to *cis*-form to form coplanar complex like.

Cl-Q

The excess electron density on the nitrogen atoms (in bipy and phen) and positive centers of Q or Cl-Q are in favourable disposition to form a six membered stable complex.

The free rotation of bipy is restricted. The complexes become stable and K_{DA} values become very close to each other and are not affected much due to variation of solvents. The stability of the complexes is due to ground state rather than excited state stabilization.

Lesser stability of the Cl-Q complexes can be attributed to steric repulsion due to the presence of Cl-atoms in the *ortho*-position.

The effects of the solvents on the Gibbs energy changes have been found to be very small but similar for both the complexes. The stability constants of the complexes have been found to be greater in aliphatic solvents compared to those in aromatic solvents. The stability constants in aromatic solvents are almost the same but in aliphatic solvents they differ slightly and the sequence is

$$K_{\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2} > K_{\text{CCl}_4} > K_{\text{CHCl}_3}$$

This is contrary to the observation that the poorest ionizing solvents give rise to the highest values of K_{DA} ($\text{CCl}_4 > \text{CHCl}_3 > \text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$)¹⁵.

The real understanding of the solvent effect is difficult

in view of a number of complicating specific and non-specific interactions like H-bonding, dipole-dipole, dispersion interactions etc. in solution and non-availability of K_{DA} -values in the gaseous state.

From the consideration of the solvation cycle for the transfer processes of the reaction from the gas phase (g) to solution (s)¹⁶.

we have

$$\Delta E_s = \Delta E_g + [\Delta E_{\text{DA(PH)}} - \Delta E_{\text{D(PH)}} - \Delta E_{\text{A(PH)}}] \quad (5)$$

assuming that the chemical interaction between D and A to be constant in different solvents for a particular complex DA. The solvent effect can be considered to arise mainly from the differences in non-specific or physical (PH) interactions.

The non-specific solvation has been assumed to be the summation of two parts :

- (i) ΔE^d – energy due to dispersion interactions and
- (ii) ΔE^c – energy due to electrostatic interactions depending on the dielectric constants of the solvents.

For the complex formation where the dispersion energy weakly depends on the solvent, the variation of Gibbs energy changes can be written as

$$\Delta G_s^0 = \Delta G_g^0 + \Delta G_d^0 - A\Delta\mu^2 \frac{(\epsilon - 1)}{(2\epsilon + 1)} \quad (6)$$

$$= \Delta G_g^0 + \Delta G_d^0 + \beta \frac{(\epsilon - 1)}{(2\epsilon + 1)} \quad (\beta = -A\Delta\mu^2) \quad (7)$$

where

$$A = \frac{4\pi N^2}{3}, \Delta\mu^2 = \frac{\mu_{\text{DA}}^2}{V_{\text{DA}}} - \frac{\mu_{\text{D}}^2}{V_{\text{D}}} - \frac{\mu_{\text{A}}^2}{V_{\text{A}}} \quad (8)$$

V = molar volume, μ^2 = reaction polarity and μ = dipole moment.

Thus, the plot of ΔG_s^0 against $(\epsilon - 1)/(2\epsilon + 1)$ should be a straight line having $(\Delta G_g^0 + \Delta G_d^0)$ as intercept and $A\Delta\mu^2$ as slope. However, two distinct lines – one for aromatic

solvents (the number of studies in aromatic solvents is only two) and other for aliphatic solvents are obtained (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1(a). Plot of ΔG^0 against $(\epsilon - 1)/(2\epsilon + 1)$ of different organic solvents. Donor: 1,10-phenanthroline, Acceptor: chloranil, Solvents: (1) benzene, (2) toluene, (3) *o*-xylene, (4) dichloromethane, (5) chloroform, (6) carbon tetrachloride.

The behaviour is exactly similar to those obtained by plotting ΔG_s^0 against $1/\epsilon$ (Fig. 2). Since ΔG_g^0 is the same for particular complex, the difference arises mainly from dispersion and electrostatic interactions. For aliphatic solvents (Fig. 1), the slope is negative or $\Delta\mu^2$ is positive ($\Delta\mu^2 > 0$)

Fig. 1(b). Plot of ΔG^0 against $(\epsilon - 1)/(2\epsilon + 1)$ of different organic solvents. Donor: chloranil, Acceptor: 2,2'-bipyridine, Solvents: (1) benzene, (2) toluene, (3) *o*-xylene, (4) dichloromethane, (5) chloroform, (6) carbon tetrachloride, (7) mesitylene.

indicating polar complex for Cl-Q + bpy complexes but due to paucity of data it is not definitely conclusive. The behaviour is exactly opposite in aromatic solvents where the slope is positive or $\Delta\mu^2$ is negative ($\Delta\mu^2 < 0$) indicating weakly polar complex. However, for Cl-Q + phen complexes, the slope is positive and $\Delta\mu^2$ is negative for both

Table 2. Charge-transfer interactions of chloranil with different solvent molecules and variations of charge-transfer energy and other properties of the solvent mixtures

Sl. no.	Solvents	$\nu \times 10^{-14}$ s	E (kcal mol ⁻¹) based on chloranil	E_T	Z	DN	AN
1.	DMF	10.96	104.55	43.8	68.5	26.6	16.0
2.	Ether	10.39	99.05	34.5	-	19.2	3.9
3.	DMSO	10.31	98.36	45.0	71.1	29.8	19.3
4.	Ethanol	10.31	98.36	51.9	79.6	20.0 (indirect)	37.1
5.	Ethyl acetate	10.28	98.02	-	-	-	-
6.	Chlorobenzene	10.21	97.34	37.5	58.0	-	-
7.	Ethylcyanoacetate	10.21	97.34	-	-	-	-
8.	Methanol	10.14	96.67	55.5	83.6	19.0	41.3
9.	Benzene	8.81	84.01	34.5	-	0.1	8.2
10.	Toluene	8.22	78.41	33.9	-	-	-
11.	Carbontetrachloride	8.00	76.29	32.5	-	-	8.6
12.	Acetonitrile	8.00	76.29	46.0	71.3	14.1	19.3
13.	Chloroform	7.91	75.48	39.1	63.2	-	23.1
14.	Dichloromethane	7.85	74.88	41.1	64.2	-	20.4
15.	<i>o</i> -Xylene	7.63	72.75	-	-	29.8	-
16.	Mesitylene	7.12	67.86	-	-	-	-

E_T = Energy value (Dimroth *et al.*); Z = Kosower's Z-value.

DN = Donor number
AN = Acceptor number

Gutmann

Fig. 2. Plot of ΔG^0 against $1/\epsilon$ of different organic solvents. Donor : 2,2'-bipyridine, Acceptor : chloranil. Solvents : Same as Fig. 1(b).

Fig. 3. Plot of ΔG^0 against $E_T(30)$ of different organic solvents. Donor : 2,2'-bipyridine, Acceptor : chloranil, Solvents : Same as Fig. 1(b).

aliphatic and aromatic solvents, i.e. complex is weakly polar. The intercepts, which differ slightly, are equal to ΔG_g^0 (Gibbs energy changes of complex formation in the gaseous phase) and the change of dispersion energy ΔG_d^0 corresponding to the gas solution transition.

In view of the similar nature of the complexes, μ_{DA} for both the complexes should be nearly the same. The dispersion interaction though opposite in case of aliphatic and aromatic solvents must be very weak in the solvents of low dielectric constant and dipole moments. The unknown gas-phase values could have provided us better understanding of the solvation effects though, the squeezing effect occurring in solution should decrease the energy of the complex relative to the gas phase. From the plots ΔG_g^0 can be regarded to be close to $\approx -11.50 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ for bipy complex and $-13.40 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ for phen complexes. However, the straight lines with different slope may be due to

- (a) Solvent effects on specific dipolar interactions,
- (b) solvent induced interactions resulting from the change in complex dipole moment μ_{DA} having different proton binding sites and
- (c) relative stabilization of the dative structure in non polar solvents and no bond structure in polar solvents.

But quantitative evaluation of these interactions is not possible.

Attempts were also made to correlate ΔG_s^0 with solvent polarity $E_T(30)$. The plot of ΔG_s^0 against E_T (Fig. 3) is similar to the plot of ΔG_s^0 vs $(\epsilon - 1)/(2\epsilon - 1)$.

The empirical parameters like the solvent polarity $E_T(30)$ defined by Dimroth and Reichardt^{17,18} (based on the solvent sensitivity of light absorption band due to intramolecular CT transition of pyridinium phenol betaine) or Kosower's *Z*-values¹⁹ (based on intermolecular charge-transfer band of 1-ethyl-4-carbomethoxy pyridinium iodide) were used for the correlation of solvent effects with equilibrium constants, spectral transitions etc. In these molecules, both ground state stabilization and increase in excited state energies occur depending on polarity of the solvents. The standard states for both ground states stabilization and excited state destabilization are not well defined and vary with solvent systems which are very much dependent on various specific and non specific interactions, the nature of which are unknown and unrelated.

According to Gutmann, *Z*- (or E_T)²⁰ values do not represent effectively the donor properties of a solvent as nearly identical *Z*-values are assigned to solvents of vastly different donor but similar acceptor properties. *Z*-values thus bear a close relationship to the acceptor properties of a solvent rather than representing a general measure of the polarity or ionizing properties of the solvent.

It is to be noted that chloranil, known acceptor, also undergoes spectral solvent shifts. Naturally, the solvent shifts are dependent on the donor properties of the solvents and energy of transitions i.e. *E*-values¹ can thus be utilized for correlation. The parameters in different solvent systems are presented in Table 2.

However, in view of different complicated interactions, E_T values or *Z*-values, *E*-values or any physico-chemical parameter are of limited utility for correlation purposes.

Experimental

Chloranil (E. Merck) was crystallised from ether and sublimed in vacuo. 1,10-Phenanthroline (phen) and 2,2'-bipyridine (bipy) (G.R., E. Merck) were used as such. The solvents (benzene, toluene, xylene, mesitylene, dichloromethane, chloroform, carbon-tetrachloride) were generally of spectroscopic quality (Sisco or SRL, India) and distilled before use.

Marked changes in absorbance and slight shift in the absorption maxima in the UV and visible regions when the components were mixed suggested complex formation. Cl-Q, bipy and phen as well as the complexes formed absorb strongly in the UV region. Naturally, the absorption measurements in the region 330–400 nm where bipy or phen do not absorb, were made to determine complex formation.

The composition of the complexes determined in few solvents had been found to be 1 : 1 by Job's method of continuous variation with some fluctuations (Fig. 1).

The complexes are assumed to be 1 : 1 in all classes as in the case of benzoquinone complexes². For the determination of the stability constants of the complexes, the components were mixed nearly in stoichiometric proportions. The absorptivity values of the mixtures and the blanks containing chloranil in the desired solvent only were noted at suitable wavelengths (given in the Table). Measurements were made with a Hitachi UV-visible spectrophotometer (Model 200-20) controlled at 298 K.

References

1. S. C. Lahiri, K. Mazumder and K. K. Mazumder, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1990, **46**, 1137.
2. R. Mondal (Karan) and S. C. Lahiri, *Z. Physic. Chem.*, 1999, **205**, 69.
3. S. C. Lahiri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 715.
4. K. K. Mazumder and S. C. Lahiri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **73**, 163; 1997, **74**, 378; 2000, **77**, 447.
5. J. Gangopadhyay, *Z. Physic. Chem.*, 2000, **214**, 169; 2001, **215**, 863.
6. S. C. Lahiri, *Z. Physic. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1974, **255**, 23.
7. D. K. Hazra and S. C. Lahiri, *Z. Physic. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1976, **256**, 497.
8. S. C. Lahiri and S. Aditya, *Z. Physic. Chem. (NF)*, 1964, **41**, 173.
9. C. C. Deb, D. K. Hazra and S. C. Lahiri, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 26.
10. K. Datta, A. K. Mukherjee, M. Banerjee and B. K. Seal, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1997, **53**, 2587.
11. B. Chakraborty, A. K. Mukherjee and B. K. Seal, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2001, **57**, 223.
12. B. B. Bhowmik and A. Bhattacharya, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1986, **42**, 1217, 1361.
13. B. B. Bhowmik and A. Bhattacharya, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1988, **44**, 1147.
14. R. H. Linell and A. Kaezmarzyk, *Z. Physic. Chem.*, 1961, **65**, 1196.
15. C. C. Thompson, Jr. and P. A. D. de maine, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 3096, *J. Physic. Chem. (Ithaca)*, 1965, **69**, 2766.
16. J. Maleki in "Molecular Interactions", eds. H. Ratajerax and W. J. Orville-Thomas, John Wiley and Sons Ltd., 1982, Vol. 3, Chap. 4; *Angas. Chem. (Int. Edu.)*, 1965, 2291.
17. K. Dimorth and C. Reichardt, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1966, **215**, 344.
18. C. Reichardt in "Molecular Complexes", eds. H. Rataze Zak and W. J. Oriville-Thomas, John Wiley and Sons, 1982, Vol. 3, Chap. 5.
19. (a) E. M. Kesower, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 3253, 3261; (b) "An Introduction to Physical Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1968.
20. V. Gutmann, "The Donor-Acceptor Approaches to Molecular Interaction", Plenum Press, New York, 1978, Chap. 2.